

**EFFECT OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT ON EMPLOYEES'
PERFORMANCE IN AN ORGANIZATION: A STUDY OF STATE LOCAL
GOVERNMENT SERVICE COMMISSION, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE,
NIGERIA.**

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of Performance Management on Employees Performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A total of one hundred and fifty (150) copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents during the study: while One Hundred and Nine (109) copies were properly filled and returned for the analysis. Data collected were analyzed using the statistical tools of linear Significantly related to organizational performance. The study recommends that there should be meaningful dialogue between superiors and subordinates about performance and improvement. Managers and supervisors should dialogue on regular basis about performance and improvement with their subordinate in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Also, the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria should establish and adopt performance appraisal system that would facilitate effective appraisal of the employees and therefore provide opportunities to the management in identifying staff training needs.

Keywords: Performance Management; Employees' Performance, Mangers; Supervisors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Performance management is the system through which organizations set work goals, determine performance standards assign and evaluate work, provide performance feedback, determine training and development needs and distribute rewards (Bajoko, 2015). Performance management is a process involving performance planning, performance managing, performance appraisal, performance rewarding and performance development (Armstrong, 2014). Roles of senior managers is to

manage and effectively deploy organizational objectives; leading organizations therefore, strive to put the right performance measurement system which is value based, that help them to agree upon performance goals and give the desired outcomes (Audu and Timothy, 2014). Organizations are run and steered by people. It is through people that goals are set and objectives are accomplished. The performance of an organization is thus dependent upon the sum total performance of its members. The success of an organization will therefore depend on its ability to measure accurately the performance of its members and use it objectively to optimize them as a vital resource (Asamu, 2013).

Presently, with the competitive environment, organizations have to ensure peak performance of their employees continuously in order to compete and survive at the market place effectively (Gungor, 2014). Performance of an individual can be defined as the record of outcomes produced as specified job functions or activities during a specified time period (Gungor, 2014). It can also be seen as a set of outcomes achieved during a certain period of time and does not refer to traits, personal characteristics or competencies of the performer (Gehart and Milkovich, 2015). Performance management on the other hand can be defined as a systematic process for improving organizational performance by developing the performance of individuals and team (Esu and Inyang, 2016) Performance appraisal can be defined as the formal assessment and rating of individuals by their managers (Boachie, 2017). Performance appraisal as an element of performance management is often carried out to reveal individual employee's contribution to the overall organizational objectives. Armstrong (2013), asserted that people do not learn unless they are given feedback on the results of their actions. For corrective actions to take place, feedback must be provided regularly and it should register both successes and failures. Therefore, this study tends to investigate whether a significant relationship exist between performance management and employee performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Performance management can also be inferred as performance appraisal which is one exercise that human resource department in organization must implement in regular basis. If performance appraisal is not carried out perfectly, it can have ripple effects on the staff and can be seen to be unfair and ineffective. Performance appraisal also has negative effects in organization and this has become an issue of concern in many organizations that have not put in place the right tools for staff performance management in order to determine whether its strategy is being achieved, thus, organization should put in place a good performance system (Hayford *et al.*, 2016).

The purpose of performance management is to help enhance productivity in organizations. It will help to measure the productivity of organizational members and it is quite paramount and sensitive in managing human resources, the reason is that, the outcome of the output of workers helps in making the organization to succeed. It is important to indicate here that, some authorities use this to downsize or underscore the efforts of workers who are not their favourites. Thus, a proven performance

appraisal process joints the work place and the workers together and show the workforce what they are expected to do and where they may function appropriately in the organization (Flecker, 2015). It is used together with the productivity of an employee to identify a worker's chance for upgrading, improvement and ranking into other high ranks of offices. Since majority of employees will like to infer the leaders' thoughts of their output places, performance assessment is necessary. Performance appraisal is also seen as a mechanism that stands in administering a place of work and a worker there, is such a way that an individual or group can attain the outlined institutional objectives (Denisi and Kluger, 2013).

The process of measuring the performance of employees in the organization is often vague, the areas of performance for which an individual is responsible are often unclear and evaluations are often not based on actual performance but on the perception and judgement of an employee's immediate boss. It is on this background that this research seeks to examine the relationship between performance management and employee's performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of performance management on employee performance, other specific objectives shall include:

- i) To examine the relationship between performance management and employees' attitude to work
- ii) To explore the nexus between performance management and organizational performance.
- iii) To examine whether performance appraisal reveals employees' actual strengths and weaknesses in the organization.

The above objectives emanate from key research questions which are:

- 1) What is the relationship between performance management and employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
- 2) What is the relationship between appraisal goals and employee performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

The following null hypothesis are set to be tested in the course of this study:

- 1) There is no significant relationship between performance management and employee performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between appraisal goals and employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Purpose of Performance Management

According to Boswell and Boudreau (2000), there are two types of functions for appraisal (management) systems, namely;

- (i) Evaluation function which includes use of performance appraisal for salary administration, promotion decisions, recognition of individual performance and identification of poor performance. To conduct this evaluative performance the appraiser takes the role of a “Judge”.
- (ii) Development functions: this includes the identification of individual training needs, providing performance feedback, Determining transfer attachments, identification of individual strengths and weaknesses. For this development function, the appraiser takes the role of a “coach or mentor”. Developmental functions focus on within person analysis. There is an increasing focus on the development's aspects of appraisal; and also, development of control and operation of the process from human resource to line managers (CIPD, 2005).

Barons (2004) claims that the focus on performance management is on elements such as recognition, constructive feedback, personal recognition and career opportunities.

2.2 A shift in Emphasis in performance Appraisal Performance Management

Gratton and Ghosa (2002) argue that at all levels, the emphasis should be on the core of the appraisal and developments process, that is “improving the quality of conversation” rather than going through “dehydrated with open rituals” with honest leaders setting the example for a culture of curious creative learning organizations. Cunneen (2006) also highlights the issue of managers disliking carrying out performance appraisal, admitting that it is the most dreaded task in their calendar.

In their book on the subject, Armstrong and Baron (2005) note in terminology in performance management, which they believe indicates a wider shift in the philosophy and content of the process. According to them: “Performance Appraisal has a reputation as a punitive, top-down control device, an involved system; Performance Management is a holistic, total approach to engaging everyone in the organization in a continuous process to improve everyone and their performance, and thereby the performance of the organizations”.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research used survey design as the strategy or plan of action regarding events which upon implementation will enable the researcher to investigate the problem of this study. The study was designed in a systematic process of providing answer to the research question. The term population refers to the entire group of individual or items whose manner or units possess the same basis and clearly defined characteristics. The size of the targeted population of this study consists of 150 staff

who are working in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

For the purpose of this research study, the Sample size of this research study is then 35 selected research participants. One of the major instruments used in collecting data for this research work is a well-designed questionnaire. Their responses will help to provide solution to the research questions which was formulated for this study; it was structured in two forms. Section (A) for personal data while Section (B) is the research questionnaire collection in order to obtain authentic and reliable information in their various department which will be useful for this research work. The study adopted simple regression technique to estimate the effect of the dependent variables on the independent variable. The statistical package which was used in this analysis was the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The result of the model was evaluated on the basis of statistical test of significant. The research result was further interpreted, discussed and analyzed in line with the research problem, hypotheses and relevant literature and experience.

4. PRESENTATION OF RESULT

The regression model was specified to capture the objectives and hypotheses of the study, the models below was formulated to capture the stated objectives in this study

Model One:

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1MAGP_i + U_i$$

Where; β_0 = constant, MAGP = Performance Management

Table 1: Linear Regression Analysis result for Model I

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.103	.105		10.518	.000
MGEP	.641	.044	.767	14.645	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EP

The Constant: From our regression result, the constant term is 1.103, which is approximately 1.10 unit. This means that if all explanatory variable in the model are held constant, on the average, employees' satisfaction will increase by 1.10 unit.

Performance Management: Here performance management is our independent variable. According to our regression result, there exist a positive relationship between performance management and employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In our result the unstandardized coefficient of management appraisal is 0.641unit, on the average, a

unit increase in performance management will lead to about 0.64 unit increase in employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Presentation of ANOVA Result

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	43.521	1	43.521	214.476	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.438	150	.203		
	Total	73.958	151			

a. Dependent Variable: EP

b. Predictors: (Constant), MGEP

The ANOVA table is used to test the overall significance of the estimated model. It is conducted to know if the independent variables in the model are statistically significant in explaining changes in employees' performance. In this case, this will be used to test effect of performance management on employees' performance of staff in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The result in the table 2 will be tested using the 0.05% level of significant. From the table 2 above, the significant value which is less than 0.05% indicate that the overall model was statistically significant in explaining changes in the employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.767 ^a	.588	.586	.45046	.580

a. Predictors: (Constant), MGEP

b. Dependent Variable: EP

This is used to test the goodness of fit of the regression results. From the regression result in the table above, the value of R² is 0.588. This means that about 59% of total variation in the dependent variable is jointly explained by the independent variables while the remaining 41% is dues to other stochastic variables not capture in the model which can be employees' welfare, working environment and condition etc. One can claim that the model shows justifiable evidence of a good fit as the adjusted R-square value of 58% reaffirm the goodness of fit of the regression model.

Model Two

$$Ep_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 APG_i + U_i$$

Where; β_0 = constant, APG = Appraisal Goal

Table 4: Regression Analysis for Model II

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.150	.121		9.542	.000
APG	.601	.051	.695	11.840	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EP

The Constant: From our regression result, the constant term is 1.150, which is approximately 1.15 unit. This means that if all explanatory variable in the model are held constant, on the average, employees' satisfaction will increase by 1.15 unit.

Appraisal Goal: Here appraisal goal is our independent variable. According to our regression result, there exist a positive relationship between appraisal goal and employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In our result the unstandardized coefficient of appraisal goal is 0.601unit. This means that a unit increase in appraisal goals will lead to about 0.60 unit increase in employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Presentation of ANOVA Result for Model II

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	28.119	1	28.119	140.196	.000 ^b
Residual	30.085	150	.201		
Total	58.204	151			

a. Dependent Variable: EP

b. Predictors: (Constant), APG

The result in the above table will be tested using the 0.05% level of significant. From the table above, the significant value which is less than 0.05% indicates that the overall model was statistically significant in explaining changes in the employees' performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.695 ^a	.483	.480	.44785	1.388

a. Predictors: (Constant), APG

b. Dependent Variable: EP

From the regression result in table 6, the value of R^2 is 0.483. This means that about 48% of total variation in the dependent variable is jointly explained by the independent variables while the remaining 52% is due to error term not captured in the model.

HYPOTHESES TESTING

Hypothesis One:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between performance management and employee's performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The hypothesis one stated above was tested using the probability value of the regression analysis in table 1. The decision rule is that if p-value of the test statistic is less than 0.05 significant level, we therefore, rejected null hypothesis and upheld alternative hypothesis. Thus, from the linear regression in table I, the probability value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Thus, we rejected the null hypothesis (H_0). This implies that performance management has a direct relationship with employees' performance and is statistically significant in explaining changes in the employees' performance.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is no significant relationship between appraisal goals and employee's performance in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The hypothesis two stated above was tested using the probability value of the regression analysis in table 4. Thus, from the linear regression in table above, the probability value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Thus, we rejected the null hypothesis (H_0) and concluded that appraisal goal has a direct relationship with employees' performance and is statistically significant in explaining changes in the employees' performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed that performance management has a direct effect on the employees' performance in State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This is in line with the opinion of Asame (2013) who found out that there was a significant relationship between performance management and employees' performance in work places. This means that, when there is a significant increase in management performance by the employees, it will likely increase their level of performance and productivity.

Besides, the study revealed that appraisal goal has a direct relationship with employees' performance. This supports the opinion of Flecher (2015) who found that there was a significant relationship between appraisal goal and employees performance in companies. This implies that when there is increase feedback on the results of peoples' actions, people tend to learn seriously.

CONCLUSION

Performance appraisal helps to enhance the productivity in organizations and it is quite paramount and sensitive in management of human resources, the reason is that; the outcome of the output of workers helps in making the organization succeed. Thus a proven performance appraisal process joints the workplace and the workers together and shows the workforce what, they are expected to do and where they may function appropriately in the organization. It is used together with the productivity of an employee to identify a worker's chance for upgrading, improvement and ranking into high ranks of offices. It can be concluded that, performance management enhances workers' productivity in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) It is recommended that; multiple appraisal method should be introduced to further encourage objectivity and eliminate bias in the appraisal of workers in the ministry.
- 2) It is also recommended that employee feedback method of performance appraisal should be a prerequisite for workers in the workplace.
- 3) The study recommends that, the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria should establish and adopt performance appraisal system that would facilitate effective appraisal of the employees and therefore provide opportunities to the management in identifying staff training needs.
- 4) The study recommends that there should be meaningful dialogue between superiors and subordinates about performance and improvement. Managers and supervisors should dialogue on regular basis about performance and improvement with their subordinate in the State Local Government Service Commission, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Armstrong, M. (2014). *Armstrong's Handbook of Performance Management. An Evidence-Based Guide to Delivering High Performance*. London: Kogan Page.
- Asamu, F. F., (2013). Perception of Performance Appraisal and Workers' Performance in Wema Bank Headquarters, Lagos. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(4), 89-101.
- Audu, J. S., and G. Timothy, 2014: Effects of Human Resource Training and Development on Productivity in Nigerian Hospitality Industry. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*, 2(2), 80-87.
- Banjoko, S. (2015). Employee Performance Appraisal; Pennant, July-Sept, 8 (3).
- Boachie-M. F., (2017). Employees' Perception of Performance Appraisal System: A Case Study. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(2), 73-88.
- DeNisi, A. S. And P. Kluger, (2013). Performance Appraisal, Performance Management and Improving Individual Performance: A Motivational Framework. *Management and Organization Review*, 2(2), 253-277.
- Esu, B. B., and B.J. Inyang, (2016). A Case for Performance Management in the Public Sector in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4 (4) , 9 8 - 1 0 5 . Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v4n4p98>.
- Fletcher, C., (2015) Performance Appraisal and Management. The Developing Research Agenda. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 4(1), 12-27.
- Gerhart, B. And G. T. Milkovich, (2015). Organizational Differences in Managerial Compensation and Financial Performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 663-691.
- Gungor, P. (2014). The Relationship between Reward Management System and Performance Appraisal for Teachers Implementation. *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), 544-559.
- Hayford, C., Y. Boakye and N. O. Ovusu, (2016). Is Performance Appraisal System Anachronistic in Tertiary Institutions in Ghana? Evidence from the University of Cape Coast. *Journal of Business and Management*, 18(4), 55-62.